

Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 5:
*Climate action, environment,
resource efficiency and raw materials*

CONSTRAIN

CONSTRAIN: 'Constraining uncertainty of multi-decadal climate projections'

GA number 820829
H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2

More information: cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820829
Project archive: zenodo.org/communities/constrain-project-820829

Work Package: WP2

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Deliverable title: Short report on main outcomes and participating organisations of the workshop on frameworks for characterizing mesoscale organisation of shallow convection

Cite as:

Stevens B., Bony S. and Siebesma P. 2021. Framework for characterizing mesoscale organisation of shallow convection. The CONSTRAIN Project. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10125097](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10125097).

Summary of results:

In (Schultz et al. 2021) four previous identified patterns of meso-scale cloud organization in the trades – called Sugar, Gravel, Flowers and Fish – as observed satellite imagery are linked to long-term records of ground-based measurements Barbados Cloud Observatory and model reanalyses. This way the local thermodynamical and cloud structure (wind, temperature, humidity, rain and cloud fraction profiles) and the large scale forcings associated with each of the four cloud patterns are now identified. The results suggest that due to the tight bound of the patterns to wind and air-mass origin, the patterns with the higher cloud fraction, Flowers and Fish, will be disfavoured in a warming climate with more equable sea-surface temperatures and fewer mid-latitude disturbances.

Instead of building further on subjective, but interpretable classes of patterns Janssens et al. (2021) used a large set of 21 commonly used metrics for 5,000 cloud fields observed by satellite over the Atlantic Ocean east of Barbados. These 21 metrics contain a large amount of redundant information: To effectively describe and interpret the cloud patterns, only four derived metrics are required: typical cloud size, the size of connected clear sky patches, the clouds' degree of directional alignment and spatial variance in cloud top height. These four metrics form a new, effective and interpretable pattern description, which can be used to better understand how cloud patterns develop and how this impacts the wider climate system. The specific cloud types, Sugar, Gravel, Flowers and Fish used in (Schultz et al. 2021) can be easily integrated into this framework.

Published works:

Schulz H., Eastman R. and Stevens B. 2021. Characterization and Evolution of Organized Shallow Convection in the Downstream North Atlantic Trades. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*. **126**(17), pe2021JD034575. DOI: [10.1029/2021JD034575](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JD034575).

Janssens M., Vilà-Guerau de Arellano J., Scheffer M., Antonissen C., Siebesma P.A. and Glassmeier F. 2021. Cloud Patterns in the Trades Have Four Interpretable Dimensions. *Geophysical Research Letters*. **48**(5), pe2020GL091001. DOI: [10.1029/2020GL091001](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091001).